

The Analytical and Numerical Characterization Regarding Indentation of Composite honeycomb Sandwich Structures

Xiaoyu Zhang, Fei Xu, Min-ge Duan

School of Aeronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China

Introduction & Problem description

Sandwich structures with composite laminates are widely used in various areas ranging from civil engineering to marine and aerospace applications because of their high stiffness-to-weight ratio, specific bending resistance and energy absorption properties. However, it has high susceptibility and vulnerability to damage caused by transverse loading. The indentation is one important failure mode and can be interactive with other failure modes.

Different damage modes:

- Facesheet damage
- **Core crushing** & shear damage
- Debonding of face/core interface

Experimental, numerical and analytical methods have been conducted to investigate the mechanical behavior of sandwich structures under transverse loading both in static and dynamic loading.

- ✓ Experiment
- ✓ Simulation
- ✓ Analytical method

- Load-displacement relationship
- Material damage

This research focus the barely visible indentation of sandwich structure through analytical method and finite element simulation.

- ✓ 3D elasticity solution
- ✓ Winkler model (Elastic, plastic)
- ✓ Vlasov model (Elastic and plastic)

The real-world out-of plane compression behavior of honeycomb structure

Analytical model

The analytical model based on Vlasov model includes the real-world crushing process of honeycomb for both elastic region and plastic region.

Vlasov model used for orthotropic material:

Equivalent orthotropic material

In plane XZ:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{13} \\ C_{13} & C_{33} \\ C_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix}$$

The corresponding total energy is:

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} b \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} D_f \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} b \iint (\sigma_x \varepsilon_x + \sigma_z \varepsilon_z + \tau_{xz} \gamma_{xz}) dA$$

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0; \varepsilon_z = \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} = w(x) \frac{\partial \phi(z)}{\partial z}; \gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \phi(z) \frac{\partial w(x)}{\partial x}$$

We can obtain the governing equation and shape function by minimizing the energy function Π with respect to w and ϕ , respectively.

$$D_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - k_1 \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + k_2 w(x) = 0$$

where $k_1 = G_{13} \int_{-t_c}^0 \phi^2 dz$; $k_2 = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta} \int_{-t_c}^0 \left(\frac{d\phi}{dz} \right)^2 dz$ $\phi(z) = \frac{\sinh[\gamma(1-z/t_c)]}{\sinh(\gamma)}$, $\gamma^2 = t_c^2 \frac{G_{13} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 dx}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} w^2 dx}$

Analytical and FE model

The sandwich beam can be separated into two region including elastic region and collapse region. The out-of-compression stress-strain curve of core in collapse as well as the plateau stress domain can be presented in following form:

$$\sigma(w) = \sigma_s + (\sigma_p - \sigma_s)(1 - e^{-\beta(w/t_c - \varepsilon_s)})$$

The differential equation in different region

Elastic $D_f \frac{d^4 w_p}{dx^4} - k_1 \frac{d^2 w_p}{dx^2} + r(w) = 0$

Collapse $D_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - \eta k_1 \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + k_2 w(x) = 0$

$$\eta = \alpha_1 \frac{\sigma_s + (\sigma_p - \sigma_s)(1 - e^{-\alpha_2 \beta(w-w_s)})}{\sigma_s}$$

The coefficient η represent the degradation of shear effect during indentation

The FE model for plat compression and indentation

The FE simulation of out-of-plane compression for honeycomb (Collapse procedure)

Discussion and conclusion

➤ Indentation result of FE model

➤ Comparison between analytical and FEM results

➤ Parameters study

The influence of parameters in the equation of the out-of-compression stress-strain curve was studied.

Results with different parameters

Conclusions

- 1) Considering the shear effects of the honeycomb, the modified Vlasov's model considering shear effect in both elastic and crush region is used to predict the response of honeycomb sandwich beam subjected to indentation.
- 2) It can be noted that basic factors of the geometry parameters, such as width of the beam, thickness of the upper face sheet might influence the indentation behavior. And the cell size of honeycomb core affecting the material properties, such as Young's modulus and plateau stress of the honeycomb core under compression can results in different indentation for sandwich structures.
- 3) Considering different honeycomb materials and structures, the key factors that have great influence on the honeycomb composite sandwich beam subjected to static indentation, are β and σ_p , which reflect the plastic deformation and plateau stress respectively.